

Original Article**Olive leaf extract and coconut oil rectal enema: a new ayurvedic therapeutical strategy for feline atopic skin syndrome****Kerem Ural*¹, Buğrahan Bekir Yağcı² Hasan Erdoğan¹, Songül Erdoğan¹**

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Abstract

Enemas, historically and traditionally, have been used for management of several disorders, as well as to proper prescribing fluids and drugs. The aim of the present study was to manage feline atopic skin syndrome by use of coconut oil and olive leaf extract via rectal enema. A total of 6 cats with Feline Atopic Syndrome presenting cutaneous reaction pattern, subclassified as face, head, neck pruritus met diagnostic criteria at this study. Initial diagnostic interventions included a) lab work (clinical findings, cytology and dermatological examination along with dermatoscopy) dietary changes (limited carbohydrate diet) c) Polychex in vitro allergy test for allergen-specific immunoglobulin E detection in serum, d) hematological/serum biochemical analytes, e) endocrine panels and f) clinical scoring by use of Feline Dermatitis Extent and Severity Index and owners assessment of pruritus using a 10 cm visual analogue scale with grade descriptors. There were statistically significant decreases throughout the study (on days 0 and 10) regarding the Feline Dermatitis Extent and Severity Index and visual analogue scale pruritus scores. Pre-treatment and post-treatment comparisons analyzed via non-parametric Wilcoxon test and parametric Paired-sample T denoted that the day 0 scores were significantly higher than the scores at day 10 ($p < 0.001$ in each case). In cats administered rectal enema olive leaf extract and coconut oil for 10 days, all had significantly decreased Feline Dermatitis Extent and Severity Index from $121,5 \pm 44,4$ to $14,0 \pm 6,0$ ($p=0.028$). Furthermore significant alterations for pruritus visual analogue scale from $6,5 \pm 2,7$ to $1,5 \pm 1,2$ ($p=0.027$). No adverse events attributable to the olive leaf extract and coconut oil therapy were reported in any of the cats, and adverse events.

Keywords: Dermatitis, nutraceutical, rectal enema, pruritis.

Introduction

Feline atopy [feline atopic dermatitis/Feline Atopic Syndrome (fAs), non-flea non-food allergic dermatitis) denotes i) type 1 hypersensitivity, ii) dermatological disorder accompanied by pruritus, iii) occurrence of immunoglobulin E (IgE) antibodies against allergens (Hnilica, 2011; Miller et al., 2013;) with a disease prevalence of 12.5% (Ravens et al., 2014). Growing evidence of analogy between fAs and atopic dermatitis in humans and dogs are being reported. Similar to atopic dermatitis in dogs, fAs accompany an amplified immunoglobulin E (IgE) and immunoglobulin G against environmental allergens (Foster

et al., 1997; Gilbert and Halliwell, 1998), whereas allergen-specific IgE analyses might not distinguish disease status by itself (Halliwell et al., 1998). Purgatory, in other words cleansing, denotes purifying of the individual which is in tradition been viewed as a place of torment, the purpose for purifying the individual. Given the frequently prescribed enema and purgatory are both unpleasant, thus both are validated for similar aim, specifically thought to clean the body. Primary care health professionals commonly perform enemas for diagnosing/treating selected diseases (Ramakrishnan and Scheid, 2003) whereas in veterinary profession it is ignored, forgotten and unknown. On the other hand, the first author of the present

manuscript easily and professionally use enema for several nutraceutical delivery to treating disorders for several years. By addressing the role of enemas for management of fAs (which was the aim of the present study), we hope to provide veterinary surgeons on the field and academy with a better understanding of their efficacy and potential, enabling them to easily and safely exercise, when considering their use. Recently treatment option of fAs has pointed that use of moisturizer, antibiotics, anti-histamine, ciclosporin and corticosteroids or fatty acids and palmitoyl ethanolamide with lower efficiency for reducing skin inflammation by changed skin barrier function and diminishing itch (Mueller et al., 2021). However the use of steroids exhibit atrophy of the skin after long term application (Schacke et al., 2002). Given that the long-term use of agents such as steroids and immunosuppressants is often associated with side effects, including extreme atrophy of the skin and sensitivity to infection (Hengge et al., 2006; Martins et al., 2015; Benaim et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2019), the development of novel therapeutic approaches using natural products with minimal adverse reactions is being actively pursued. The use of kind of natural compounds using has increased for therapeutic purposes due to they contained several bioactive molecules exhibiting beneficial roles including antioxidative, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial property on health (Hajam et al., 2019).

Olive leaf extract (oLe), a naturally extracted product from olive leaves, contains oleuropein (olp) and other bioactive phenolic compounds. Olp was identified to have various medical properties (El and Karakaya, 2009, Kishikawa et al., 2015, Qabaha et al., 2018, Chanyachailert et al., 2017). It was also found to inhibit the effects of both acute and chronic UVB-induced skin damage as well as accelerate wound healing activity (El and Karakaya, 2009, Kishikawa et al., 2015, Qabaha et al., 2018, Chanyachailert et al., 2017). On the other hand, beneficial effect of coconut oil (coiL) was described in Figure 1.

Enemas, historically and traditionally, have been used for management of several disorders, as well as to proper prescribing fluids and drugs. The responsible author and his teammates of the present study have been using rectal route for administration of selected nutraceuticals and probiotics for a very long time. Though mainly thought to relieve constipation by the veterinarians, accor-

ding to the present authors' knowledge and evidenced articles, it has era of application for management of several different conditions. The aim of the present study was to manage feline atopic skin syndrome by use of coiL and olive leaf extract oLe via rectal enema.

Figure 1: Beneficiary effects of coconut oil in dermatology (Varma et al., 2018).

Materials and methods

Study era

The present study was conducted at the University of Aydin Adnan Menderes, Faculty of Veterinary, Department of Internal Medicine. A total of 6 cats with Feline Atopic Syndrome (fAs) presenting cutaneous reaction pattern, the were classified as face, head, neck pruritus (fHnD) (Santoro et al. 2021). The latter article well described algorithm for fAs. This subclassification comprising fHnD itching behaviour in association with face, head and neck erosion, ulceration and excoriation (Santoro et al. 2021), which are criteria met at this study. Major differential diagnosis involving miliary dermatitis, self-induced alopecia, eosinophilic granuloma complex (Santoro et al. 2021) were all excluding factors in the present study. Initial diagnosis based on history, clinical findings, cytology and dermatological examination including dermatoscopy. Flea control was available in 6 cats. All cats were and adviced to be fed on a low carbohydrate diet involving % 17.5 carbohydrate (Virbac digestive) for at least 6 weeks. One of the other inclusion criteria was that no prior drug administration was evident, Polychek in vitro allergy test for allergen specific IgE detection in serum (Polychek; Biocheck GmbH, Germany) was available for all cats, as this

assay run 20 different allergens. Hematological and serum biochemical analytes were deemed available (data not necessary to show). Plasma cortisol, total thyroxine values were analyzed for 5 out of 6 cases, which deemed reference ranges.

Data interpretation

Clinical signs of feline head and neck dermatitis were scored using a FeDESI (Nuttall et al., 2014) The owners assessed pruritus using a 10 cm visual analogue scale with grade descriptors (Hill et al., 2007). From day 14, the owners independently scored ease of use, tolerance, and efficacy from 1 (very poor) to 5 (excellent).

Trial protocol; nutraceutical compounds Coconut oil and olive leaf extract

Olive leaf extract and coil obtained from a commercial nutraceutical company (Vetnacare, Aydın, Turkey) with pure compounds. Both natural products were purchased just prior to study, freshly, and specifically originated to this researched, not even commercially available at the moment. Both products were 97% pure and organic. Rectal enema procedure was similarly adapted from previous methodology (Ural et al., 2021a,b). Briefly both natural ingredients, namely nutraceuticals, were combined in sterile water at stable room temperature (therefore mixed) as water in oil. Afterwards as was shown in Figure 2. Foley catheter was inserted from rectum up to 15 cm distance, followed by gentle application of water in oil nutraceuticals composed of oLe and coil. This procedure was applied or advised for 10 days duration, in which every step was under record. Full clinical assessments were performed on days 0 and 10 at referral to our Faculty Clinic.

FeDESI were deemed available for scoring of clinical lesions (i.e. erythema, excoriations/erosions and self-induced alopecia) (Nuttall et al., 2004; Schmidt et al., 2012). The owners assessed pruritus via a ten cm VAS involving descriptors (Hill and Rybnicek, 2007). At each referral during 10 days duration responsible veterinary surgeon checked for number of treatment applications, side effects or other necessary information.

Statistical analysis

Intentions to treat data were described. All data obtained from study were evaluated in SPSS 20.0 (IBM, USA) and $p < 0,05$ value set as statistically significant. Box plot graphs shows 25 and 75 percent slices, whiskers show 10 and 90 percent slices. Homogeneity tests were performed with Shapiro- Wilk.

Pre-treatment and post-treatment comparisons were detected via non-parametric Wilcoxon test and parametric Paired-sample T test according to the homogeneity results.

Figure 2: Administration procedure of coil and oLe via rectal route.

Results

Demographic data

A total of 6 cats, at the age of 1.5 to 7 years, of both sexes, were enrolled. This was self-controlled, randomized prospective trial, which was performed along with PhD students along with Covid-19 precautions (mask, hygiene and social distancing). Four were neutered females and 2 others were intact males.

FeDESI and VAS pruritus scores

There were statistically significant decreases throughout the study (on days 0 and 10) regarding the VAS pruritus (Figure 3) and FeDESI (Figure 4) scores (Table 1). Pre-treatment and post-treatment comparisons analyzed via non-parametric Wilcoxon test and parametric Paired-sample T denoted that the day 0 scores were significantly higher than the scores at day 10 ($p < 0.001$ in each case). In cats administered rectal enema oLe and coil for 10 days, all had significantly decreased FeDESI from $121,5 \pm 44,4$ to $14,0 \pm 6,0$ ($p=0.028$). Furthermore significant alterations for pruritus VAS from $6,5 \pm 2,7$ to $1,5 \pm 1,2$ ($p=0.027$). No adverse events attributable to the oLe and coil therapy were reported in any of the cats, and adverse events. Clinical photographs of some cases were shown in Figures 5-7 describing prior and after treatment.

Figure 3-4 : Box plot analyses to thereof VAS pruritus and FeDESI scores among enrolled cats with atopic skin syndrome.

Figure 5 : Weekly recorded (from week 1 to 5th) clinical records, in that feline atopic skin syndrome was responsive to olive leaf extract and coconut oil, extraordinarily given via rectal route.

Figure 6 : Weekly recorded (from 1 to 4) clinical photographs in which cat with atopic skin syndrome was responsive to olive leaf extract and coconut oil rectal enema.

Figure 7 : A well reponder cat to the protocole deemed available in the present study. Photographic evidence was available prior to and thereafter 10th day post-treatment

Table 1 : Statistical analytes pre- and after-treatment.

	<i>Pre-Treatment (Median ± SD)</i>	<i>Post-treatment (Median ± SD)</i>	<i>P value</i>
VAS Score	6,5 ± 2,7	1,5 ± 1,2	0,027
FeDESI Score	121,5 ± 44,4	14,0 ± 6,0	0,028

Discussion

Disease management for fAs is life-long and generally composed of various treatment options (trials) and lifestyle alterations. Regarding the severity of fAs, an individualized therapeutical plan might be designed. Symptomatic anti-pruritic prescriptions with glucocorticoids or cyclosporine are accepted beneficial in providing cats' comfort. On the other hand, potential adverse effects [(life-threatening cardiac reflection (2), diabetes and urinary tract infection (Bajwa, 2018))] may be observed. Apart from those aforementioned side effects, and the disadvantages of immunosuppressive trials, the target of our study was to prescribe a novel way (rectal route) of a therapeutical strategy involving oLe and coiL, in which we thought that this probable treatment modality would highlight treatment armamentarium of atopic dermatitis patients, also in human being, as a role model. This natural compounds without any immunosuppressive effects, rather might have immunomodulatory efficacy (Veza et al., 2017).

This study shows that a novel nutraceutical combination involving oLe and coiL in which rectal administration appeared to be a highly effective treatment for fAs, subclassified as fHnD. There were marked reductions in both clinical lesions and pruritus as detected by FeDESI and VAS pruritus cores, respectively. All 6 cases enrolled, achieved clinical remission with varying degrees related to enema treatment and significant alterations on pre- and post-treatment median ± SD FeDESI scores [121,5 ± 44,4 vs. 14,0 ± 6,0 (p=0,028)]. The FeDESI and pruritus scores tended to significantly decrease, suggesting that the rectal enema oLe and coiL therapy caused remission among clinical lesions, and that this obtained improvement was to the authors' knowledge relevant to the efficacy might be due to oLe's antibacterial/antifungal, anti-inflammatory and wound healing properties ((El and Karakaya, 2009; Kishikawa et al., 2015; Chanyachailert et al., 2017; Qabaha et al., 2018) as shown in Figure 1. Moreover, pre- and post-treatment median ± SD

VAS pruritus scores tended to decrease markedly [6,5 ± 2,7 vs. 1,5 ± 1,2, respectively, (p=0,027)].

Given olive leaves composed few oleic acids along with a marked polyphenol ingredient (Poudyal et al., 2010), in which olp as one major phytochemical compound exist in large amount (Manna et al., 2004; Corona et al., 2006). Available evidence suggested that olp presented several pharmacological activities in vitro (i.e. anti-inflammatory and antioxidants effects) (Manna et al., 2004; Miles et al., 2005). Furthermore, indistinguishable efficacy was also denoted in vivo, as olp along with major metabolites caused nitric oxide production, altered blood pressure and impeded platelet aggregation in animal models (Visioli et al., 1998; Visioli et al., 2002; Al-Azzawie and Alhamdani, 2006).

In a prior study with experimentally induced murine atopy model, olp extract and spirodela polyrhiza extract ameliorated atopic dermatitis by decreasing i) serum IgE levels, ii) immune /inflammatory cells along with Th2 cytokines and iii) repairing the expression of skin barrier-related proteins (Lee et al., 2020). Extracts of the leaves of olp presented preventive efficacy against UVB-induced skin damage (Sumiyoshi and Kimura, 2010). Data regarding olp evidenced that this compound is able to interact with different molecular targets participated within the inflammation. Although not analyzed, as this was a self-funding study without external financial support, olp might mitigate underlying low grade systemic inflammation probably existed in the present cats.

Apart from aforementioned data a prior study conducted to search polyphenol compounds involved in oLe were in charge of stimulating probiotic bacteria growth and metabolism and whether if same efficacy was deemed available on desirable components of the intestinal microflora. Given the big question 'phenolic compounds belonging to food and plants even if modulate gut microbiome' should meet increased selective elevation of lactobacilli and bifidobacteria along with deport of clostridia and other harmful bacteria (Haddadin,

2010) possessing 400% higher antioxidant capacity than vitamin c (Ryan and Robards, 1998). Several conclusions were deemed available composing the efficacy of polyphenol compounds (to those of rich plants) on gut microbiota, in which plant extracts hamper food pathogens together with gut microbiota (Mobe et al., 1999; Nagayama et al., 2002; Kim et al., 2004; Medina et al., 2006). Moreover, ole has prebiotic activity (Bello et al., 2001; Molan et al., 2009), in which its ethanolic extract supported the growth of *B. infantis* and *L. acidophilus* (Haddadin, 2010). The initial author of this manuscript has been working on the field of gut microbiome for several years, however due to financial limitations, gut microbiota 16 s rRNA analysis were not deemed available in this study. In fact, lacking analysis could not rule out the possibility of prebiotic efficacy of oLe and its influence on gut microbiome, would have hasten recovery among cats enrolled in this study.

Someone (without prior experience, who might think having idea, out of knowledge) may speculate the rectal route of olp that we used in this study. However, a brief discussion should be made. Regarding the bioavailability of olp, the probability that the latter biophenols might present their biological efficacy in relation to possible delivery of key molecular targets in tissues at an adequate concentration, that depends on their metabolism and bioavailability. Indeed, metabolic data on olp or olive leaves in human beings are poor (Visioli et al., 2000; Miró-Casas et al., 2001; Vissers et al., 2002). The bioavailability of olp is dominated by various conditions, i.e. administration route, age, genotype, sex, interaction with nourishment, several extraction process and analytical methods performed (Lemonakis et al., 2016). Available data indicated that oral olp consumption is resistant to the acidic environment of the stomach, and it is quickly absorbed (55–60%) within the intestinal tract (de Bock et al., 2013). As data on metabolization, degradation products, absorption and metabolism kinetics once ingested, is lacking both in humans and cats more studies are warranted. Therefore, results of this study, specifically delivered olp in rectal route would have hastened clinical recovery, which would be a role model for future research. We have competing interest for larger scaled studies. Furthermore, and as a significant data, olp administration protected the hypothalamus from oxidative stress via ameliorating mitochondrial function (Sun et al., 2016).

Conducting to a search on literature, one of the in-

teresting articles was that topical coconut oil was used successfully for long-term treatment of diversion colitis (Zundler et al., 2018). In that study daily usage of coconut oil for 6 months resulted within continuous clinical respond, without any observable adverse events. Furthermore, topical application of coconut oil was suggested as a therapeutical option for diversion colitis (Zundler et al., 2018). Regarding the efficacy of coconut oil involves fatty acids with comparatively short chain length (Orsavova et al., 2015), the latter are not alike within the short chain fatty acids confirmed within diversion colitis treatment, though they are commensally produced and reduced in the inflamed mucosa (De Preter et al., 2015) suggesting a positive impact on epithelial metabolism as postulated for SCFAs (Harig et al., 1989). Indeed, cell death studies with the colon epithelial cell line HT29 demonstrated that coconut oil, but not other oils exclusively consisting of fatty acids with long chain length (Orsavova et al., 2015), substantially decreased epithelial cell necrosis.

The rectum, with an ignored and unknown 'to the present authors' knowledge' potential might be alternative route for the ingestion/administration of food, fluids and drugs (Heath, 2001). In the first century Dioscorides A.D. suggested giving "wine of mandragora," via rectal route against (Mckechnie, 1998). Rectal administration of opioids (Scherlis, 1981), liquid ether and vapor (Mckechnie, 1998) has historically well known. To date probiotics (D'Inca et al., 2011; Amit-Romach et al., 2015; Ural et al., 2021) has recently been used as a novel methodology via rectal route. Besides in a recent study the authors used nutraceuticals along with probiotics via rectal route for treatment of pruritus to those dogs with atopic dermatitis (Ural et al., 2021). In the present study both nutraceuticals were well tolerated by rectal route without any adverse effect. This novel treatment modality would have hastened clinical recovery among fAs cases, given administration in the present study.

Coconut oil, traditionally extracted from the kernel/meat of mature coconuts, is reaped among the coconut palm (*Cocos nucifera*). Coconut involves several free fatty acids with different percentages ranging from 49% lauric acid to 2% both, linoleic acid and stearic acid (Sahle et al., 2015). coiL has been used in dermatology as a moisturizer (Agero and Verallo-Rowell, 2004), against atopic dermatitis (Evangelista et al 2014) and wound healing (Nevin and Rajamohan, 2010). Proved evidence aroused our interest, in which we decided to use coconut oil as a one part of our therapeutical strategy in this study.

In a paediatric model, mild to moderate atopic dermatitis was treated with topical (virgin) coconut oil, which effectively decreased disease severity. In addition, disease severity index was altered, and barrier function was improved (Evangelista et al., 2014). Kim et al. (2017) demonstrated that coiL increased expression of cornified cell components, thereby contributing to protective barrier functions of the skin. Furthermore, the expression of inflammatory profile was lower in the coiL-treated group after exposure to UVB radiation (Kim et al., 2017). Topical coiL protects the skin from UV radiation (Korac et al., 2011). In the present study as 6 cases were enrolled, achieved clinical remission at different levels in association with enema treatment. This therapeutical strategy was evidenced by decreased post-treatment median $\pm$ SD FeDESI scores ($14,0 \pm 6,0$) in contrast to pre-treatment values ($121,5 \pm 44,4$) ($p=0,028$). The FeDESI and pruritus scores [$6,5 \pm 2,7$ vs. $1,5 \pm 1,2$, prior to and after-treatment values, respectively, ($p=0,027$)] all supported positive influence of this rectal enema oLe and coiL treatment modality in the present study.

Of all the acid components of coconut oil, monolaurin has been shown to have additional significance. Monolaurin is a monoglyceride derived from lauric acid. It comprises nearly 50% of coconut's fat content. Monolaurin displays antimicrobial activity by disintegrating the lipid membrane of lipid-coated bacteria including *Propionibacterium acnes*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (Preuss et al., 2005). Coconut oil in concentrations of 5% to 40% (w/w) exhibited bactericidal activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris*, and *Bacillus subtilis* (Oyi et al., 2010). Cellular studies have also shown that monolaurin exhibits antiviral and antifungal activity (Esquenazi et al., 2002). In the present article although viral or fungal lab work was not performed, due to the nature of the disease activity, monolaurin could display antimicrobial (and that of antiviral/antifungal) activity against possible secondary cutaneous dysbiosis, among cats enrolled.

Previous evidenced proof of olp existed intestinal anti-inflammatory activity in colitis (mouse models, maybe be related to its immunomodulatory properties and the capacity to restore the intestinal epithelial barrier. Besides, the extract could also regulate the activity of cells involved in the inflammatory response.

The health benefits of such polyphenol-rich plants are mainly related to their secondary metabolite

contents, and they are expected to exhibit complementary effects (Nam et al., 2017; Ozcan et al., 2017). Different combinations of natural products and/or their repositioning have been reported, and several interesting extracts and compounds have been identified, such as those of *salvia miltiorrhiza* and *pueraria lobata* (coronary heart disease) and artemisinin-based combinations (*Artemisia annua* L.) (WHO, 2006; Cheung et al., 2012; Zhou et al., 2016). Therefore, the combination of oLe and coiL via rectal route represents a promising therapeutic approach for fAS.

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